

CoARA Report and Action Plan 2022-2024

Membership

In November 2022 the Swedish Rectors' Conference, the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions, SUHF, applied for membership in CoARA.

Activities

National Working Group

In 2022, SUHF appointed a working group with the task of developing a national framework for merit assessment at Swedish higher education institutions, triggered also by the call for an updated Open Science strategy.

The framework is in working progress and is planned to be endorsed by the General Assembly in October 2024.

During the spring 2024 there will be seminars, workshops and other types of activities on a national level.

National Chapter

There is an increasing awareness among Swedish higher education institutions and major funders that current standards for assessing research merits have major limitations and is not fully reflecting how science is performed today and how research output is disseminated.

Swedish signatories of CoARA have therefore agreed to work at the national level to identify common standards for assessment of research. SUHF has taken actions to establish a National Chapter by gathering universities and funders together with other stakeholders.

We see advantages in gathering the overall national work together within a National Chapter, and we intend to actively contribute our on-going work and implemented "good examples" with the whole CoARA family.

The application will be sent for approval in the end of 2023 or in the beginning of 2024.

During 2024 the National Chapter will start planning, promoting, and sharing ideas and work towards the implementation of new standards and models. The planned work is as follows:

- One annual face-to-face meeting for members of the National Chapter, first meeting planned beginning of 2024;
- Formation of working groups with specific tasks (to be defined and agreed on by members at the first meeting in 2024);
- Digital meetings at a regular basis in the working groups;

- Formation of CoARA mirror groups to stimulate work and progress at individual member organisations and with the possibility for smaller organisations to arrange the work as networks;
- Establishment of a digital platform for sharing information and news to the whole Swedish research community;
- Sharing the Swedish work and experiences with the whole European CoARA community.

Nomination to the CoARA Steering Board

SUHF has in November 2023 nominated Professor Jan-Ingvar Jönsson, Vice-Chancellor Linköping University, to the CoARA Steering Board for two years.

CoARA Working Groups

There are altogether ten Working Groups in CoARA. SUHF is taking part in one of them.

The Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA) is based on the premise that ACA systems should adequately reflect the different tasks, functions and roles academics fulfil over the course of their career. The aim is to broaden the reflection on research assessment to ACA, taking into account the full range of work conducted by academics in research, teaching and learning, innovation, management/leadership and service to society. Contact: Rita Morais, EUA.